

Development of Woven Cut-Resistant Fabrics Using Core-Sheath Composite Yarns with Stainless Steel and Glass Fiber Cores

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Abstract

This study investigates the functional properties of protective woven plain, twill, and Sateen fabrics to understand their suitability for specialized applications. In this research work composite yarns are fabricated using core as E-glass and stainless-steel metal filament with diameters of 0.025, 0.050, 0.060 and 0.075 mm, combined with polyester and high-performance polyethylene as sheath materials. The research focuses on developing a protective woven fabric by core-to-sheath ratios to enable analysing key parameters such as cut resistant, tensile strength, abrasion resistance, stiffness, and air permeability, with an emphasis on the impact of weave structures on these properties. The findings reveal significant variations in performance based on fabric type, highlighting the strengths and limitations of each weave pattern. This research findings aim to guide textile engineers and designers in selecting appropriate weave structures for specific industrial, medical, and protective applications, ensuring an optimal balance of durability, functionality, and usability.

Keywords

Woven Cut Resistance Fabric, Mechanical Properties, Resistance, Air Permeability Properties.

Introduction

The textile industry has placed significant emphasis on the development of high-performance cut-resistant fabrics to meet the growing demand for advanced personal protective equipment (PPE) in sectors such as construction, manufacturing, and law enforcement^{1,2}. Traditional cut-resistant materials, including metal mesh and heavy-duty fabrics, often suffer from rigidity and excessive weight, compromising wearer comfort and mobility^{3,4}. To overcome these limitations, core-sheath composite yarns have emerged as a promising solution, integrating high-strength core fibres viz. stainless steel or glass with flexible sheath materials viz. polyester and HPPE to enhance both protection and wearability⁵⁻⁷.

Objective of study

This study investigates the cut resistance of woven fabrics produced using core-sheath composite yarns with varying core materials and weave structures. Stainless-steel wires fibres of three different diameters (0.025, 0.050, and 0.070 mm) and glass fibres (0.050 mm) cores were incorporated into plain, twill, and Sateen weave configurations to evaluate their mechanical performance.

Review of Literature

Composite yarns containing metal wires are used for two main purposes. The first usage area is for functional purposes like protection, health, communication or automation as a technical yarn. Metal-based conductive composite yarns, which can be used to develop smart textiles and electrotiles, are being increasingly considered for the fabrication of conducting textiles. Bedeloglu et al. measured the hairiness and tensile properties of composite yarns produced by wrapping copper and stainless steel-based wires around cotton yarn¹⁷. Örtlek et al. investigated the physical properties of hybrid yarns containing copper wire which are produced with 5 different production methods at three different twist levels¹⁸. Perumalraj and Dasadaran produced copper core spun yarns of different counts on Dref friction spinning and modified ring spinning machines and investigated the effects of the process variables on tensile properties of these yarns¹⁹.

Main Text

The selection of weave structures is critical, as previous research has demonstrated that fabric structure significantly influences cut resistance⁸. Woven fabrics have emerged as particularly promising due to their ability to combine mechanical durability with wearer comfort⁹. However, the performance characteristics of these fabrics are fundamentally determined by their structural parameters, with weave pattern representing a critical design variable that directly influences tensile strength, abrasion resistance, and flexibility^{1,6-8}. Plain weave, known for its tight and balanced structure, has been reported to exhibit the highest resistance to knife penetration due to its maximum fibre coverage^{8,10}. In contrast, twill weave, characterized by its diagonal rib pattern, offers a compromise between flexibility and protection, while Sateen weave, with its long float

yarns, prioritizes drape and comfort but may reduce cut resistance¹¹⁻¹³. Despite these findings, a systematic comparison of these fundamental weave structures in relation to cut-resistant performance remains lacking in the literature. This gap is particularly significant given the growing demand for specialized protective textiles in industries

Stainless steel core yarns were selected for their high tensile strength, durability, and additional functional properties, including thermal resistance and electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding¹⁴. The varying diameters of Stainless-steel wires (0.025, 0.050, and 0.070 mm) allowed for an impact assessment of fibre thickness on cut resistance. Glass fibres (0.050 mm) cores, while providing exceptional stiffness and tensile strength, are inherently brittle and prone to breakage, limiting their long-term durability in wearable textiles¹¹⁻¹³. To mitigate this issue, glass fibres were bundled with polyester or high-density polyethylene in the sheath to improve flexibility and wearability¹⁵.

The comparative analysis of core materials and weave structures revealed that stainless steel cores are expected to deliver superior long-term durability, whereas glass fibre cores may offer higher initial cut resistance but degrade faster under mechanical stress. Additionally, a few researchers mentioned that plain weave fabrics demonstrated the highest cut resistance, followed by twill and satin weaves¹⁰. Some researchers observed that sateen weave demonstrate the highest cut resistance among other samples¹⁶. These findings contribute to the optimization of woven cut-resistant fabrics for PPE applications, balancing protection, flexibility, and comfort. Future research should explore hybrid core materials, advanced weaving techniques, and real-world durability testing to further enhance the performance of these textiles.

Methodology

This research follows a comprehensive manufacturing approach beginning with the production of core-sheath composite yarns using stainless steel wires (FSS) fibres of three different diameters (0.025, 0.050, and 0.07 mm) and glass fibres (FGF-50) (0.050 mm) as core components, encapsulated within polyester and high-performance polyethylene (HPPE) sheath materials. These specialized yarns were manufactured at High Performance Textiles Pvt. Ltd. (Panipat, India) employing advanced hollow spindle spinning technology to ensure optimal core encapsulation and yarn integrity. The resultant composite yarns were subsequently woven into three distinct fabric architectures - plain, twill, and Sateen weaves - using a shuttle sample loom. Table 1 shows the fabric specification.

Table 1: Specifications of Woven Cut-Resistant Fabrics

Fabric Code	Core Material (µm)	Weave	EPI	PPI	GSM	Thickness (mm)	Yarn count Denier	Cover factor
FSS-25	0.025 mm Stainless steel wire	Plain	68	52	192	0.61	400	23.4
		Twill	68	52	205	0.62	400	23.4
		Sateen	68	52	201	0.66	400	23.4
FSS-50	0.050 mm Stainless steel wire	Plain	42	38	279	0.77	740	21.9
		Twill	42	38	285	0.77	740	21.9
		Sateen	42	38	284	0.79	740	21.9
FSS-75	0.070 mm Stainless steel wire	Plain	42	38	331	0.80	940	23.6
		Twill	42	38	332	0.84	940	23.6
		Sateen	42	38	323	0.87	940	23.6
FGF-50	0.050 mm E-Glass fibre	Plain	42	38	308	0.88	840	22.8
		Twill	42	38	322	0.92	840	22.8
		Sateen	42	38	322	0.97		

The mechanical properties of the protective fabrics were rigorously evaluated through standardized testing protocols. Tensile strength of protective fabric measure in both warp and weft directions were conducted following ASTM D5035 guidelines, utilizing an Instron 3365 universal testing machine configured for constant rate of extension (CRE) principle. Rectangular specimens (200 mm × 50 mm) were stretched at a controlled speed of 20 mm/min. Young Tearing strength is evaluated in both the directions (warp and weft) following ASTM D 1424. Test specimens measuring 8 inches x 3 inches are prepared, with five specimens tested in each direction.

Cut resistance performance is quantified according to BS EN ISO 13997, which evaluates material resistance against sharp object penetration under controlled conditions. The testing matrix, including all applicable standards, is systematically presented in Table 2.

Table – 2 Requirement as per BS EN 388:2016+A1.2018

Clause/Test Name	Level A	Level B	Level C	Level D	Level E	Level F
TDM: cut resistance (N)	2	5	10	15	22	30

The air permeability assessment is conducted using a TESTEX TF 164-A automated testing system following ASTM D737 standards. Measurements quantified airflow in SI units (cm³/s/cm²), representing the volumetric air passage through a 1 cm² fabric area per second under a standardized 127 Pa (1 cm water column) pressure gradient. Testing employed a 5 cm² adapter ring for consistent specimen loading. Abrasion resistance is evaluated using a Martindale pilling and abrasion tester according to BS EN 388:2016 +A1 2018. The specimen size is specified as having a diameter of 38 ± 5 mm, while the abradant size is defined with a diameter of 14.5 ± 2 cm. The test conditions for both the woven and knitted fabric samples are maintained at 9 KPa. During testing, the specimen undergoes a cyclical rubbing motion up to 8000 cycles, which results in stress development along the fibre due to surface friction. Fabric stiffness is determined in both warp and weft directions using the cantilever bending test method as outlined in ASTM D 1388. Test specimens measure 25 cm x 2.5 cm.

Result and Discussion

Effect on mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of woven fabrics, particularly tensile and tear strength, serve as critical indicators of their performance in practical applications. This study examines four fabric codes (FSS-25, FSS-50, FSS-75, and FGF-50) with three distinct weave types (plain, twill, and sateen) to evaluate their structural durability. Table 3 shows the tensile and tear strength properties of different fabric samples. FSS-50 exhibited the highest tensile strength values in both the warp (489.4–525.7 kgf) and weft (328.1–418.1 kgf) directions, indicating superior resistance to tensile forces. This enhanced performance may be attributed to higher thread density or superior fiber quality.

Table 3: Mechanical Properties of Different Fabric Constructions

Fabric Code	Construction Type	Tensile strength (kgf)		Tear strength (kgf)	
		Warp way	weft way	Warp way	weft way
FSS-25	Plain	308.5	149.2	67.4	71.1
	Twill	303.7	286.8	109	99.1
	Sateen	270.7	265.3	99.7	96.6
FSS-50	Plain	489.4	357.3	137.9	150.1
	Twill	469.9	418.1	133.4	173.4
	Sateen	525.7	328.1	135.3	159.3
FSS-75	Plain	340.9	232	136.9	148.9
	Twill	270.2	289.1	136.4	199.1
	Sateen	336.8	287.5	152.2	165.2
FGF-50	Plain	317.9	194.8	118.5	99.9
	Twill	199.6	221.8	112.8	103.5
	Sateen	363.5	290.7	117.2	117.2

In contrast, FSS-25 demonstrated the lowest tensile strength in the weft direction for plain weave (149.2 kgf), suggesting a structural vulnerability. The FGF-50 samples consistently underperformed relative to FSS fabrics, with twill weave showing the weakest tensile strength (199.6 kgf warp, 221.8 kgf weft). Variations were observed within the FSS-75 samples, where tensile strength differed significantly between twill (270.2 kgf warp) and sateen (336.8 kgf warp) constructions. This difference underscores the influence of weave geometry on mechanical behavior. Additionally, the comparatively lower strength metrics of FGF-50 fabrics suggest a potential trade-off between cost-efficiency and mechanical robustness. Figure 1 reveals that tensile strength varies significantly across fabric structures (Plain, Twill, Sateen). Warp direction consistently shows higher tensile strength compared to weft, indicating structural orientation significantly impacts strength distribution

Figure 1: Effect of different fabric structure on tensile strength properties

Tear resistance varied significantly across weave types. Sateen weaves, particularly FSS-75 sateen, displayed the highest tear strength (152.2 kgf warp, 165.2 kgf weft), likely due to their long float yarns, which distribute stress more effectively. Conversely, plain weaves, especially FSS-25, recorded the lowest tear resistance (67.4–71.1 kgf), a consequence of their tightly interlaced structure that concentrates stress. Twill weaves exhibited intermediate performance, with FSS-50 twill achieving notable weft tear strength (173.4 kgf), indicating balanced durability. The findings demonstrate that both material composition and weave structure critically influence the mechanical properties of woven fabrics. Sateen weaves and FSS-50 fabrics consistently outperformed other variants, making them ideal for high-stress applications. It is observed from figure 2 that tear strength consistently exhibits higher values in the warp way compared to the weft way across all fabric types. This indicates the warp yarns have tighter packing and structural reinforcement during the weaving process. Twill fabric samples show better tear strength due to their diagonal structure, distributing stress uniformly and enhancing resistance.

Figure 2: Effect of different fabric structure on tear strength properties

Effect on stiffness and abrasion resistance

From table 4 it has been observed that Stiffness increased progressively from FSS-25 to FSS-75 in both warp and weft directions, with FSS-75 plain weave showing the highest values (1224.51 mg/cm² warp, 2028.33 mg/cm² weft). This suggests that higher-density fabrics (e.g., FSS-75) resist deformation more effectively. Sateen weaves consistently exhibited the highest stiffness (e.g., FSS-75 sateen: 1469.41 mg/cm² warp), followed by twill and plain weaves. This aligns with the structural role of float yarns in sateen weaves, which reduce inter-yarn friction and enhance rigidity. FGF-50 fabrics showed the lowest stiffness values among all tested fabrics (280.66-567.28 mg/cm²), significantly lower than even FSS-25 (492.66-1001.10 mg/cm²). Sateen weaves typically exhibit higher stiffness due to yarn dominance in one direction whereas twill weaves, with diagonal interlacing exhibits balance flexibility and rigidity.

Table 4: Effect of Construction Type on Fabric Stiffness and Abrasion Resistance

Fabric Code	Construction Type	Stiffness (mg/cm ²)		Abrasion resistance (%)
		Warp Way	Weft Way	
FSS-25	Plain	492.66	834.63	7.61
	Twill	541.93	918.09	7.81
	Sateen	591.19	1001.20	7.94
FSS-50	Plain	776.89	1162.42	8.11
	Twill	854.58	1278.66	8.25
	Sateen	932.27	1395.90	8.37
FSS-75	Plain	1224.51	2028.33	11.49
	Twill	1346.96	2231.16	11.59
	Sateen	1469.41	2434.58	11.71
FGF-50	Plain	280.66	436.37	13.32
	Twill	322.76	501.83	13.41
	Sateen	364.86	567.28	13.52

Abrasion resistance of the FGF-50 fabrics demonstrated the highest abrasion resistance (13.32–13.52), likely due to synthetic fibre composition (e.g., polyester blends) that inherently resists wear. For FSS fabrics, abrasion resistance improved marginally with weave complexity (plain < twill < sateen). For instance, FSS-75 sateen (11.71) outperformed its plain weave counterpart (11.49), indicating that float yarns may mitigate surface friction. It is also observed from the stiffness and abrasion resistance of FGF-50 samples that flexible fabric may better absorb mechanical stress during abrasion. Figure 3 illustrates the stiffness properties of different fabric types—Plain, Twill, and Sateen—in both warp and weft directions, across fabric samples FSS-25, FSS-50, FSS-75, and FGF-50. From figure 3 it is obvious that the fabric stiffness is highly dependent on weave structure and directional orientation. Sateen weaves deliver optimal stiffness for applications requiring enhanced mechanical resistance, while Plain weaves are more flexible, catering to less rigid use cases. T

Figure 3: Effect of different fabric type on stiffness

Effect on cut resistance and air permeability

From table 5, it has been observed that the cut resistance is maximized in high-density fabrics. FSS-50 and FSS-75 achieved the highest cut resistance (up to Level F for sateen), indicating superior fibre density or material toughness. FGF-50 showed intermediate performance (Level D–F), likely due to synthetic fibres prioritizing flexibility over cut protection. In case of Sateen weave the long floats allow stainless-steel wires to align parallel to blade motion, forcing blunt-edge sliding. However, the plain and twill weave type create weak interlocking resistance points allows the frequent blade snagging. Sateen weave samples show higher cut resistance because of its compact surface and float yarns that resist blade penetration. Furthermore, the air permeability is correlated with the cut resistance. From table 5, as cut resistance levels increase the air permeability values decreases. FSS-75 sateen (Level F) has the lowest permeability (522.6 mm/s), while FSS-25 plain (Level C) allowed better airflow (69.7 mm/s). Whereas the twill weave samples offer balanced performance (FSS-50 twill: Level F cut resistance, 361.3 mm/s air permeability).

Table 5: Effect of fabric type on cut resistance and air permeability

Fabric Code	Construction	Cut Resistance (N)	Cut Resistance Protection Level	Air Permeability (mm/s)
FSS-25	Plain	10.7	Level C	69.7
	Twill	12.8	Level C	290.6
	Sateen	15.4	Level D	314.1
FSS-50	Plain	30.2	Level E	63.3
	Twill	33.3	Level F	361.3
	Sateen	34.2	Level F	375.2
FSS-75	Plain	34.4	Level F	331.2
	Twill	37.6	Level F	459.5
	Sateen	38.6	Level F	522.6
FGF-50	Plain	19.6	Level D	58.2
	Twill	22.9	Level E	274.3
	Sateen	30.3	Level F	326.3

From Table 6 it has been observed that Fabric Code and construction type has a very significant effect on cut resistance. It is also observed that both factors independently affect the cut resistance significantly. Similar results are observed in case of air permeability property. Both Fabric Code and Construction Type have statistically significant effects on air permeability. The p-values < 0.05 indicate strong evidence that these factors influence the result. Figure 4 indicate a significant relationship between fabric weave types and its functional properties. It is also observed that air permeability values are drastically changes in case of twill and sateen fabric as compare to plain fabric samples.

Figure 4: Effect of different fabrics on cut resistance and air permeability

Table 6 : Two-way ANOVA analysis for the cut resistance and air permeability property

Property	Source	Sum of Squares	df	F-value	p-value
Cut Resistance	Fabric Code	996.90	3	99.96	0.000016
	Construction Type	69.62	2	10.47	0.011042
	Residual	19.95	6		
Air Permeability	Fabric Code	94,674.60	3	20.17	0.0016
	Construction Type	1,48,516.98	2	47.46	0.0002
	Residual	9,388.53	6		

Conclusion

This study shows that the weave structure has a strong effect on the protective performance of fabrics made from stainless steel wire, glass fibre, polyester, and high-performance polyethylene. Based on the results of the two-way ANOVA, both fabric code and weave type had a significant influence on cut resistance and air permeability (p < 0.05). Among the different weaves, sateen construction provided the highest cut resistance, reaching 38.6 N, and also showed good air permeability up to 522.6 mm/s. Twill weaves also performed well, with cut resistance up to 37.6 N and air permeability of 459.5 mm/s. In comparison, plain weaves had the lowest cut resistance, starting from 10.7 N, although they maintained moderate air permeability.

Overall, both sateen and twill weaves gave better cut protection than plain weaves, with increases of around 25–70%. These improvements came with only a small drop in air permeability. This shows that changing the weave type can improve safety without greatly reducing comfort.

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